

Tuning of Genetic algorithm parameters for Plan and Vertical Irregular RC buildings

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Abstract

This work presents the use of evolutionary algorithms to minimize the stiffness eccentricity and thereby optimize the seismic torsional performance for three-dimensional asymmetrical reinforced concrete buildings. In order to achieve torsional stiff structures, efforts have been made to attain an ideal automatic design of the torsional drift of the storeys of reinforced concrete buildings with plan and vertical irregularities. The torsional drift response of storeys is caused by both static and dynamic loads and they can be precisely described in terms of the design variables for the orientation of vertical structure elements. To illustrate the effectiveness and viability of the suggested optimization strategy, three examples were attempted successfully. The procedures outlined in the current seismic standards were followed to evaluate these structures performance. Mathematical modelling and Finite element analysis were utilized to perform seismic assessments of the said asymmetrical buildings. The orientation optimization issue was resolved with the use of Genetic Algorithm model. The outcomes confirmed that the proposed Genetic Algorithm (GA) can solve the orientation optimization problem for three-dimensional reinforced concrete asymmetrical buildings in an efficient and optimal manner. The study is found to be very productive as the stiffness eccentricity and torsional irregularity ratio gets reduced significantly.

Keywords: Stiffness eccentricity, Configuration of centers, Asymmetric structure, Non-linear Time History analysis, Torsional drift, Torsional Irregularity Ratio, Genetic Algorithm.

1. Introduction

Earthquakes pose significant dangers and challenges due to their destructive and unforeseeable nature, impacting human life in diverse and grave ways. It's crucial to analyse how buildings, especially their torsional behaviour, behave during earthquakes, and there are different solutions available to mitigate these effects and strengthen the structural elements, which are briefly explained; moreover, applying a genetic algorithm (GA) to optimize the design of structural members and to determine the impact and the overall response of buildings under earthquake loads by taking into account various parameters during the structural

design process. In the present study, the design parameter utilized is torsional irregularity with the objective of minimizing the eccentricity between the centre of mass (CM) and the centre of rigidity (CR) of the building by reducing the storey torsional drift.

Goldberg (1989)^[1] was among the pioneers in employing a genetic algorithm to address engineering optimization problems. According to Goldberg's work, several authors have successfully applied genetic algorithms to achieve optimal designs of structural elements. Many assessments have been performed have considered cost to the structural optimization of reinforced concrete structures and most of them allotted to cost. For example, Camp et al. (2003)^[2,3] applied a genetic algorithm for optimum flexural design of simply supported beams, uniaxial columns, and multi-storey frames by using a search for discrete-valued solutions of members in reinforced concrete frames. Govindaraj and Ramasamy (2005)^[4] reported of a detailed study on the optimal design of the RC continuous beams with the genetic algorithm. Guerra and Kiousis (2006)^[5] applied nonlinear programming (NLP) techniques for the optimal design of reinforced concrete structures. Ghodrati et al. (2008)^[6] introduced a genetic algorithm model in the optimal design of RC frames. Hatindera et al. (2014)^[7] made the assumption that all columns are rectangular and that cost optimization is carried out while adhering to IS:456-2002 standard for strength and serviceability of the structure. Alex and Kottalil (2015)^[8], applied a genetic algorithm for the optimal design of an RC continuous beam. Samruddha and Patel (2017)^[9], studied flat slab optimization using a GA. Fayaz Basha and Madhavi Latha (2018)^[10] conducted an analysis on the optimization of the RC slab design using a genetic algorithm. Sadat and Arslan (2021)^[11] examined the optimum eccentricity design for seismic applications using a genetic algorithm. In their study, the effectiveness of the genetic algorithm was examined and reported to give good solution. Sadat (2021)^[12] assessed the optimization and modelling of the effect of plan irregularity on the seismic behaviour of buildings with artificial intelligence systems. Sadat (2022)^[13] also assessed the approach of the genetic algorithm in the prevention of torsional irregularities in RC structures.

There have been several assessments on torsional irregularity including geometric asymmetry. Özmen (2004)^[14] has examined the geometrical and structural aspects of the torsion irregularity in accordance with TEC 2007. De Stefano and Pintucchi (2008)^[15] proposed a summary of the progress in research regarding the seismic response of plan and vertically irregular buildings. Özmen et al. (2014)^[16] have dictated the conditions for an excessive torsion irregularity in accordance with the TEC and explored the relevant provisions of the code. Their survey was conducted on six typical structural groups with distinct shear wall positions, axis numbers, and storeys. It was noted that the ratio of torsional irregularities decreased as the number of floors increased. Anagnostopoulos et al. (2015)^[17] examined the torsional response of non-symmetric buildings under earthquake excitations; making their design for earthquake actions considerably more complicated than the design of symmetric buildings whose response is purely translational. Mishra and Dubey (2017)^[18] studied the effect of reducing storey drift in severe earthquakes, which can cause the breakdown of structures in higher seismic zones.

It was observed based on the literature review carried out, that the previous studies were more focused on the study of torsional responses for low rise buildings and is limiting to plan irregularity only and few

researchers attempted to study the performance of low to medium rise buildings with shear walls placed at different locations. It was also reported by researchers on studying the dynamic characteristics effect of the low to medium rise buildings having asymmetric plan with stiffness eccentricity. Accordingly, it was inferred that importance on studies on seismic response of vertical irregular structures using Non-Linear dynamic analysis method through arrangement of lateral force resisting elements in the structure is important and attempt has been made in that direction.

In order to study the stated objective, in the present study; optimization method was adopted for the design solution of the seismic torsional drift for asymmetrical building has been attempted based on a G.A. approach. In order to illustrate the methodology attempted; three 3D finite element models of five and ten-storey RC buildings were considered to prove the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed optimization methodology. The models were explored with FEM Computer Programming using Equivalent Seismic Load (ESL) and mode superposition methods. The Genetic Algorithm (GA) was used as a solution to the orientation optimization problem. In the optimization problem, the orientation angles of the columns were considered as the design variables.

2. Plan and Vertical Irregularity

The design and construction of irregular buildings are generally avoided due to their adverse seismic behaviour and various irregularities in the elevation and plan. However, based on the practical considerations and aesthetic constraints, irregular structures cannot be avoided. Irregularities in plan consist of five different types: Torsion irregularity, Re-entrant corners, Floor discontinuity, Nonparallel systems and Out-of-plane offsets in vertical elements. Irregularities in elevation consists of seven types: Stiffness irregularity, Mass irregularity, Vertical geometric irregularity, In-plane discontinuity in vertical elements resisting lateral forces, Strength irregularity, Floating columns and Irregular modes of oscillations in two principal plan directions as per seismic codes of practice i.e.; IS: 1893-2016^[19].

2.1 Torsional Irregularity: Torsional irregularity is one of the most significant factors as it causes severe damage to building structures. The torsional irregularity factor (η_{bi}), defined for either of the two orthogonal earthquake directions as the ratio of the maximum storey drift at any storey to the minimum storey drift at the same storey in the same direction, is greater than 1.5 as given by IS: 1893-2016^[19]. The torsional irregularity is determined from the following equation.

$$\eta_{bi} = \frac{(\Delta i)_{max}}{(\Delta i)_{min}} > 1.5 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where: $(\Delta i)_{max}$ is the maximum storey drift and $(\Delta i)_{min}$ is the minimum value of storey drift for the i'th storey obtained from analysis under earthquake forces.

Torsion is generated when the centre of rigidity (CR) and centre of mass (CM) in the building are non-concurrent; the distance between these two centres is called eccentricity according to Duggal (2013)^[20]. The centre of mass is generally the geometric centre of the floor (in plan). The position of the centre of rigidity depends on the properties of the lateral load-resisting system components such as shear walls,

moment frames, braced frames, etc. Torsional effects can only occur in buildings with rigid diaphragms. While the structural centre of mass is affected by seismic loads, the structural centre of rigidity responds to these loads. According to Duggal (2013)^[20] if the eccentricity between these two centres is greater, a moment of torsion occurs around the centre of rigidity and the structure starts to rotate around the axis of rigidity. This moment of torsion generates additional shear forces. The behavioural response of such a structural system under seismic load conditions mainly depends on its overall shape, angle, and geometrical arrangement of the vertical members such as shear walls and columns.

2.2 Storey Drift: The storey drift ratio is the maximum relative displacement of each floor divided by the height of the same floor, which is an important parameter to measure torsion. The lateral drift performance of a building is achieved by combining the peak modal response using the Square Root of the Sum of Squares (SRSS) and Complete Quadratic Combination (CQC) rules, not to exceed 0.02 h as per IS: 1893-2016^[19].

2.2.1 Limitation of Relative Storey Drifts: In the design of earthquake-resistant structures, it is necessary to limit lateral storey drifts of a building. Extreme drifts may cause structural and non-structural damage to buildings. Reduced relative storey drift, Δ_i , of any vertical member such as a column or structural wall shall be calculated by equation (2) as the difference of displacements between the two consecutive stories as per IS: 1893-2016^[19].

$$\Delta_i = d_i - d_{i-1}, \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\delta_i = R\Delta_i, \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where, d_i and d_{i-1} , represent lateral displacements obtained from the analysis according to reduced seismic loads at the ends of any column or structural wall at storeys i and $(i-1)$. Effective relative storey drift, Δ_i , for columns and shear walls of the i^{th} storey of a building for each earthquake direction is achieved from (3). The maximum value of effective relative storey drifts, Δ_i , within a storey, $\Delta_{i, \text{max}}$, calculated by equation (4) for columns and shear walls of the i^{th} storey of a building for each earthquake direction shall satisfy the condition given by

$$\frac{(\Delta_i) \text{max}}{h_i} \leq 0.02 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

If the condition specified by equation (4) is not satisfied at any storey, the earthquake analysis shall be repeated by increasing the stiffness of the structural system as per IS: 1893-2016^[19].

3. Genetic Algorithm

The genetic algorithm (GA) is the most famous evolutionary algorithm (EA) so far, according to Rao (2009)^[21] it is an approach to model genetic evolutionary mechanisms based on the principles of survival and adaptability of the fittest. The purpose of the GA is to meet a better functional operation process that includes reproduction, crossover, and mutation. GAs use function values in the search process to progress towards a solution regardless of how functions are assessed. Continuity or differentiation of the functions of the problem is neither necessary nor used in algorithmic computations. Thus, the algorithms are very general and applicable to all types of problems such as discrete, continuous, and no differentiable. The central principle

of a GA is to generate a new set of designs (population) from the existing set to improve the average fitness of the population. The operation continues until a stop criterion is met or the number of iterations reaches a specific limit. The important steps associated with the GA model are described briefly here.

3.1 Algorithm for Optimal Drift: In this section, the proposed algorithm is described.

3.1.1 Plot Options: PlotFcn specifies the plot function or functions called at each stage of iteration by GA.

3.1.2 Initial Population: In genetic optimization algorithm, the initial population refers to the first set of candidate solutions which are generated randomly by the algorithm. This population will serve as the starting point for the further evolutionary process. Population size denotes the number of individuals that are available in each generation.

3.1.3 Evaluation: Evaluation refers to the process of assessing the fitness or quality of each individual (solution) in the given set of population. The evaluation function, also known as the fitness function, it assigns a fitness value to each individual based on its objective function value or its performance. The evaluation function is used to assess the quality of each solution, compare the solutions and selecting the best ones and guiding the evolutionary algorithm to search the better solutions.

3.1.4 Fitness scaling: Fitness scaling is a process that transforms the raw fitness scores that returns by the fitness function into a more suitable form (values in range) for selection function and reproduction. The goal here is to maintain a healthy and diverse population, preventing a premature convergence of the objective function and improve the search efficiency of the evolutionary algorithm.

3.1.5 Fitness Assignment: Several options like rank scaling, top scaling, linear scaling, log scaling and inverse scaling exist to assign fitness. In a rank-based fitness assignment, the design variable is ranked based on its objective values.

3.1.6 Selection: It is the process of choosing the individuals from the current set of population to form the next set of generation. This is one of crucial step in the GA algorithm, as it determines which individual will reproduce next offspring and pass their genetic information to the next set of generation. The selection process of the design variables is based on Darwin's theory of evolution; the best ones should survive and generate a new design variable. Roulette wheel selection, uniform selection, tournament selection, elite selections are some of the selection options available in GA algorithm.

3.1.7 Reproduction: It is the process of creating new individuals from the selected parents. This involves combining the genetic information (chromosomes) of the parents to create new individuals with a combination of their characteristics and this is how the genetic algorithm creates new children for the next generation. In this case, the three mechanisms (selection, crossover, and mutation) are involved that are discussed below, are used to create the next generation.

3.1.8 *Crossover*: Crossover options describe how the genetic algorithm combines two strings of design variables (parents) to form a crossover child for the following generation. It is genetic operator and is also known as recombination. Single-point crossover, multi-point crossover, uniform crossover, and intermediate crossover are some of the crossover options available in GA algorithm. It is a scalar value ranging between 0 and 1 that determines the fraction of offspring created by crossover versus mutation. Higher crossover fraction favours exploration of new solutions through crossover, whereas lower crossover fraction favours exploitation of existing solutions through mutation.

3.1.9 *Elite Count*: Elite count specifies how many design variables with the greatest fitness values in the present generation are guaranteed for survival in the following generation. Elite count is an integer value that determines the number of elite individuals to be retained. It is a parameter that represents the number of fittest elite individuals to be preserved and carried over to the next generation without undergoing crossover or mutation. Setting this elite count too large may lead to premature convergence, while setting it too small may not effectively preserve the best solutions.

3.1.10 *Mutation*: It is one of the genetic operators in GA optimization that introduces random genetic changes to an individual's chromosome value. This helps in introducing new genetic information, increases population diversity and avoids premature convergence of GA algorithm. Mutation process is controlled by mutation rate which ranges from 0 to 1. Each species is "mutated" at a random location. The basic idea of using this operator is to introduce some diversity into the population. Mutation Gaussian, Mutation Uniform, Mutation Adaptive are some of the mutation options available in GA algorithm. Mutation rate parameter controls the probability of mutation occurring. A higher mutation rate increases the likelihood of mutation, while a lower rate reduces it.

3.1.11 *Optimization Criteria*: The algorithm terminates criteria including generation number, computational time limit, and functional tolerance. The algorithm stops once either of these conditions is fulfilled. When optional generations are increased, the ending result is often improved.

3.1.12 *Multiple Runs for a Problem*: Since genetic algorithms make decisions in multiple locations depending on the generation of random numbers, when the same problem is executed at different times, it can give different end designs. According to Rao (2009)^[21] and Arora (2012)^[23] it is recommended to run the problem several times to make sure that the best possible solution has been achieved.

4. Numerical Analysis

To illustrate the torsional behaviour in RC structures through GA, three multi-storey examples are provided. In the first example, the structural system consists of 5 floors, whereas, in the second example, the system consists of 10 floors. In these examples, first of all, for irregular buildings, mathematical modelling and finite element analysis were developed to examine the seismic performance of buildings. After the analyses, some outputs were taken and processed using GA approach. The slabs were modelled with shell elements. The slabs were modelled as a rigid diaphragm to restrict all the nodes on each floor and to facilitate equal plan displacement. Generally fixed supports were used for columns in all directions to make simple

model. The main objective of achieving realistic outcomes, the dimensions of the structural members was calculated through a primary design procedure. Automatic generation of meshes enabling efficient meshing of all elements was used, and the meshes were sufficiently thin to satisfy the model's accuracy. The dynamic response of a vertical asymmetrical building having various eccentricities was first compared to assess the effects of the torsion response. After the analysis was carried out the structural will be obtained and responses such as torsion ratio, displacement and for drifts; optimization algorithms were used to determine good parameters. The structural optimization method for the 3D RC building structure accordingly is proposed. In the present study, optimizing the drift of the floors is formulated and applied by utilizing GA. The member angles were considered as the design variables. The lateral storey drift of the structure is regarded as an objective function to satisfy the seismic code provisions. GA repeatedly changes a set of solutions throughout its entire run until a violation is detected, the objective function $f(x)$ will not be subjected to penalties. The algorithm was terminated when the number of generations reached the maximum number of generations as per the selected value. To terminate the return operations, the generating variables should be a minimum of 90–95% similar. The buildings were resolved three times, and among the optimal solutions achieved for each set, the best solution was regarded as the optimal design. As for the final design application, the most suitable sections are selected to satisfy IS 456-2000 and IS 1893-2016 code provisions based on static and dynamic linear analysis. In all test cases the project parameters of the models and seismic details of the structure's models are tabulated in Table 1 and in Table 2 shows various GA parameters used for the optimization of process controllers. Various models of five and ten stories with total heights of 15 and 30 m are considered.

Table 1: Assumed Preliminary Data Required for the Analysis

S.No.	Variable	Data
1	Type of Structure	Special Moment Resisting Frame
2	Number of Stories	5 Storey & 10 Storey
3	Typical Storey Height	3 m (Bottom Story Height = 3.6 m)
4	Materials	Grade of Concrete - M30 & Grade of Steel - Fe550
5	Thickness of Slab	127 mm
6	Size of Beams	300 mm x 500 mm
7	Size of Columns (Basic model)	5 Storey: 300mm x 450mm; 10 Storey: 300mm x 600mm
8	Dead Load	Self-weight of members; Super Dead Load = 1 kN/m ²
9	Live Load	Live Load = 3 kN/m ² ; Roof Live Load = 2 kN/m ²
10	Earthquake Data (Linear Static Analysis)	Zone Factor: 0.36 (Zone V) Importance factor: 1.5; Response reduction factor: 5 Site type: II

Table 2: A set of solver parameters selected to resolve the case study

Number of Stories	5-Storey & 10-Storey
Number of Variables	8
Population Size	500, 3500
Mutation Function	Mutation Power
Crossover Function	Crossover Two Point
Crossover Fraction	0.8, 0.75
Number of Elite Members	25, 175
Max Generations	800
Stall Generation Limit	100, 800

4.1 Loads of the Structure and Load Combinations: The structures are subjected to horizontal loads obtained from the superposition of the seismic design mode according to [19] approach. The storey weight consists of the dead load and 25% of the live load (for residential buildings according to IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 at the time of the earthquake). The assumed super dead and live loads on the slab for each floor are 1 kN/m² and 3 kN/m² and for the roof is 2 kN/m², respectively. The following load combinations (25) are considered, and the model is analysed for the critical load condition [19].

$$P_d = 1.5 \text{ Dead} + 1.5 \text{ Live}; P_d = 1.2[\text{DL} + \text{IL} \pm (\text{EL}_X \pm 0.3\text{EL}_Y)] \text{ and } 1.2[\text{DL} + \text{IL} \pm (\text{EL}_Y \pm 0.3\text{EL}_X)]; P_d = 1.5[\text{DL} \pm (\text{EL}_X \pm 0.3\text{EL}_Y)] \text{ and } 1.5[\text{DL} \pm (\text{EL}_Y \pm 0.3\text{EL}_X)]; P_d = 0.9\text{DL} \pm 1.5 (\text{EL}_X \pm 0.3\text{EL}_Y) \text{ and } 0.9\text{DL} \pm 1.5 (\text{EL}_Y \pm 0.3\text{EL}_X); \dots(5)$$

where P_d is the required strength of a member for resisting factored loads based on load combination. A total of twenty-five types of load combinations are considered in the analysis.

The algorithm is applied using GA model running a Ryzen 5 3.00 GHz processor with 16 GB of Random-Access Memory (RAM). Each solution case of the example problems was run several times and passed different CPU times.

Example 1. Design optimization of the five and ten-storey buildings with six spans in the horizontal direction (along the X-axis) and 4 spans in the vertical direction (along the Y-axis) comprising 35 column elements. There is only a single group of storeys as the plan layout of the columns is the same for all storeys, and the vertical structural elements are divided into 5 and 10 groups of columns, thus each population has a total of 8 variables. Consequently, there is 40 and 80 design variables present in the optimization problem. In this implementation, the size of the columns is taken as 300 mm x 450 mm for a 5-storey building and 300 mm x 600 mm for a 10-storey building. The current model's plan geometry has 5 m spans and 4 m spans of projecting dimensions on the X and Y-directional axes. All the beam cross sections are 300 mm x 500 mm.

Figure 1 shows the typical floor plan, and figures 2 and 3 show elevation and 3D view of the asymmetric structures that are taken into consideration for the stiffness and torsional analysis. In these models to induce vertical stiffness irregularity (Soft story) the bottom story height is taken as 3.6 m instead of default 3 m as

assumed. The column variables marked as C1, C15, C21, C29, C32, C35, C4 and C7 are taken into consideration and the results of the example are listed and compared. The results of the optimisations are presented in the following:

The GA convergence graph is illustrated in Figure 5, where the optimum design is reached in 800 generations. After 20 iterations, which were identified as termination criteria, and at a CPU time of about 20 hours the optimum solution with the number of function evaluations 4000 was obtained.

For 5-storey models, show the orientation of columns in degrees and a comparison of initial and optimal solutions, its objective uses Gaussian and Power functions for variation in population, generation and crossover and the initial and optimal member angles for best penalty value of all considered parameters relating to stiffness and torsional irregularity for non-linear time history analysis, respectively. The orientation of columns in degrees and a comparison of initial and optimal solutions, it's objective uses Gaussian and Power functions for variation in population, generation and crossover, whereas table 10 shows a comparison of initial and optimal member angles for best penalty value of all considered parameters relating to stiffness and torsional irregularity for non-linear time history analysis, respectively.

As a result, in all the storeys the stiffness and torsional irregularity of the optimum design were significantly decreased using the introduced optimization process.

5. Optimization Problems

5.1 Formulation of Optimum Design: In formulating the optimal design problem, it is necessary to identify the design variables of the structural system, the objective function must be reduced to a minimum, and the design constraints must be applied to the system. A discrete structural optimization problem can be indicated as follows (6) [21, 23]:

$$\text{Find } x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n] \text{ which minimize } f(x) \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Subject to the constraints

$$g_j(x) \leq 0; j = 1, 2, \dots, m,$$

$$x^{iL} \leq x_i \leq x^{iU}; i = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

In the present work the design variable x indicates section angles of columns., $f(x)$ is termed the objective function, and $g_j(x)$ is the inequality constraint x^{iL} , x^{iU} are both n -length vectors containing the lower and upper limits of the computational variables, respectively.

5.2 Orientation Optimization: The aim of structural sizing optimization is generally to provide optimum cross-section angles for the individual structural elements.

6. Optimal Eccentricity Performance Design of 3D Buildings with Irregular Plan

6.1 Objective Function: The objective function for minimizing the eccentricity employed in the present work is:

$$\text{Min Eccentricity} = (\text{ecc}(X)^2 + \text{ecc}(Y)^2)^{0.5} \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

Subject to $g_j(x) \leq 0; j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ (behavioral)

$$x^{iL} \leq x_i \leq x^{iU}; i = 1, 2, \dots, n, \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

where $\text{ecc}(X)$, $\text{ecc}(Y)$ are the eccentricities between centre of mass and centre of rigidity in the orthogonal directions, respectively. The vector function $g(x)$ returns a vector of orientation 'm' which are the behavioural constraints imposed by the seismic and reinforced concrete structure design codes, x_L and x_U are the lower and upper bounds of the angles in degrees, respectively.

7. Results and Discussions

When the program was started during the optimization process; the selected design variable values were assigned to the selected column section in the pre-prepared system, the system was solved, and the objective function was calculated, thus the torsional eccentricity was minimized. Evolution will continue until the pre-determined generation number is completed. At each generation, the fitness value decreases from the first generation to the next generation as the objective function is minimized and the number of generations reaches a specified limit. As each generation progresses, population variables become more successful. Column orientation values (angles) were printed onto an output file as each generation progressed. As for the final design application, the members of this generation (angles of column) with better fitness values were taken as the optimum point.

The results show that the angles for the optimized solution are different than those of the applied ones. In these tables, the angles of the columns are denoted in degrees in a clockwise and anti-clockwise direction with positive and negative signs respectively.

To compare the initial and optimal design, after the implementation of the optimization process on 3D five and ten-storey RC buildings, the optimum design was obtained. The optimum results reveal that by using the automated design process, a design candidate can be achieved associated with the minimum eccentricity and torsional irregularity ratio that conforms to the standard code's provisions. As seen from the figures in both solutions, it was observed that the torsional irregularity ratios for all storeys were less than 1.5 in the x and y direction.

Fig 1: Typical Floor Plan of 5 & 10 Storey Models

Fig 2: Elevation and 3D View of 5-Storey Model

Fig 3: Elevation and 3D View of 10-Storey Model

7.1 Variation in Population (5-Storey):

The variation in population was carried out from 200 to 1000 with two varying mutation functions (Gaussian & Power). The results of the outcome are shown in the below graph.

Fig. 6.1: Variation of Population and Objective

It can be observed from the graph that the power function achieves the objective at 400 populations whereas the Gaussian function achieves the same objective at 450 populations.

7.2 Variation in Generations (5-Storey):

The variation in a generation was carried out from 60 to 800 with two varying mutation functions (Gaussian & Power). The results of the outcome are shown in the below graph.

Fig. 6.2: Variation of Generation and Objective

It can be observed from the graph that the power function achieves the objective at 70 generation whereas the Gaussian function achieves the same objective at 700 generation.

7.3 Variation with Crossover (5-Storey):

The variation in the crossover was carried out from 0.6 to 1.0 with two varying mutation functions (Gaussian & Power). The results of the outcome are shown in the below graph.

Fig. 6.3: Variation of Crossover and Objective

It can be observed from the graph that the power function achieves the objective at 0.7 crossover whereas the Gaussian function achieves the same objective at 0.85 crossover.

7.4 Variation in Population (10-Storey):

The variation in population was carried out from 200 to 20,000 with two varying mutation functions (Gaussian & Power). The results of the outcome are shown in the below graph.

Fig. 6.4: Variation of Population and Objective

It can be observed from the graph that the power function achieves the objective at 600 population whereas the Gaussian function achieves the same objective at 3500 population.

7.5 Variation in Generations (10-Storey):

The variation in a generation was carried out from 100 to 1000 with two varying mutation functions (Gaussian & Power). The results of the outcome are shown in the below graph.

Fig. 6.5: Variation of Generation and Objective

It can be observed from the graph that the power function achieves the objective at 150 generations whereas the Gaussian function achieves the same objective at 700 generations.

7.6 Variation with Crossover (10-Storey):

The variation in the crossover was carried out from 0.6 to 1.0 with two varying mutation functions (Gaussian & Power). The results of the outcome are shown in the below graph.

Fig. 6.6: Variation of Crossover and Objective

It can be observed from the graph that the power function achieves the objective at 0.85 crossover whereas the Gaussian function achieves the same objective at 0.75 crossover.

7.7 Final GA Parameters (10-Storey):

Table 11: A set of solver parameters selected to resolve the case study

Number of Stories	5-Storey & 10-Storey
Number of Variables	8
Type of Optimization Technique	Genetic Algorithm
Population Size	500, 3500
Mutation Function	Mutation Power
Crossover Function	Crossover Two Point
Crossover Fraction	0.8, 0.75
Number of Elite Members	25, 175
Max Generations	800
Stall Generation Limit	100, 800
Time Limit	Inf (Default)
Function Tolerance	0.1 (Default = $1e^{-06}$)

Table 12: Torsional Irregularity Ratio

Story	TIR-Basic Model	TIR-Modified Model
5-Story	1.54	1.5
10-Story	1.55	1.5

8. Conclusions

This paper develops a genetic algorithm for designing RC buildings with plan and vertical irregularities to produce torsionally balanced structures. The structural optimization method for a 3D RC frame system is proposed, and a prepared programming optimizer is utilized as an optimization solution. For this purpose, three 3D finite element models of five and ten-story RC buildings were presented to illustrate the efficiency and practicality of the proposed optimization method. The storey eccentricity response generated by non-linear dynamic analysis is explicitly expressed in terms of vertical structural element's angle design variables. The conclusions can be summarized as follows:

- (1) In the design optimization problem, the orientation of the sections of the vertical elements of the structures was generated considering the initial angles as zero, consequently, at all steps of optimization, the minimum storey torsional irregularity of the structures was achieved. In all of the storeys, the eccentricity between the CM and the CR decreases with a decrease in the design storey torsional eccentricity ratio. The torsional eccentricity ratio for different eccentricities between the CM and the CR gives an indication of the enhanced seismic requirement on the structure while satisfying the IS 1893 (Part 1): 2016 code provision.
- (2) The design variable (angle) has a significant impact on optimum objective function values. An increase in design variable angle causes a large increase in computation time but a small decrease in the objective function values.

(3) The GA optimization technique can automatically and progressively improve a performance-based torsional eccentricity design to achieve optimum performance and generate minimum torsion response. Moreover, we concluded that GA optimization can be an effective and powerful tool for the structural optimization of reinforced concrete structures.

(1) The GA optimization technique can automatically and progressively improve a performance-based torsional eccentricity design to achieve optimum performance and generate minimum torsion response. Moreover, we concluded that GA optimization can be an effective and powerful tool for the structural optimization of reinforced concrete structures.

(2) The GA optimization technique can automatically and progressively improve a performance-based torsional eccentricity design to achieve optimum performance and generate minimum torsion response. Moreover, we concluded that GA optimization can be an effective and powerful tool for the structural optimization of reinforced concrete structures.

(3) To achieve a more precise solution, we have increased the population size and maximum generation options from their default values and decreased the elite count and operating tolerance options. Moreover, increasing the initial population size will lead to a better convergence graph and a better optimum solution.

(4) It is important to note that the best objective function value may improve, or it may get worse by selecting different operators. Selecting a good set of operators for a problem is often best done by engineer experimentation.

(5) Optimum population sizes for 5 and 10 story model with Gaussian function are 450 and 3500 respectively. Whereas with power function values are 400 and 600 for 5 and 10 story models.

(6) Optimum generation values for 5 and 10 story model with Gaussian function are 200 and 350 respectively. Whereas with power function values are 70 and 150 for 5 and 10 story models. Using power function objective value stabilized after 70 generations for 5 story model and 350 generations for 10 story models. For 5 and 10 story model objective value stabilized after 700 generations with Gaussian function.

(7) Optimum cross over values for 5 and 10 story models using gaussian function are 0.85 and 0.75 respectively. Whereas with power function values are 0.70 and 0.85 respectively.

Data Availability

Data supporting the results of this study have been carefully reviewed and can be found in the text and in Tables 1 and 2 above.

Conflicts of interest

The author declares that they have no conflicts of interest.

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